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Article**STUDENTS' VERSUS TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVE
REGARDING TEACHING METHODOLOGIES IN ALLAMA
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Abstract:

Background: Till now mostly students' perspectives have been obtained regarding teaching methodologies in medical schools but in our study we attempted to conduct a comparative study to find out perceptions and preferences of both teachers and students.

Objective:

- To evaluate the satisfaction level regarding current teaching system in our college.
- To find out both the preferred and least preferred teaching methods.
- To do a comparative analysis of students' and teachers' perceptions.

Material and Methods:

Study Design: Cross-sectional study.

Study Setting and duration: We conducted our study in Allama Iqbal Medical College (AIMC), Lahore for the duration of 3 months I-e April to June 2016.

Inclusion criteria: Only students of MBBS were randomly selected. Similarly only those members of faculty were given questionnaires who teach MBBS classes.

Data Collection and analysis: Out of 175 respondents 100 were students and 75 were teachers. Collected data was analyzed using SPSS version 21.0 and various statistical formulas were applied.

Results: The stats regarding satisfaction level of current teaching system in AIMC showed that among students 33% agree and 5% strongly agree with it whereas among teachers 53.7% agree and 2.7% strongly agree with it.

Conclusions: Teachers and students are not fully satisfied with the current teaching methodologies in AIMC. Both preferred animation based lectures, practical session, problem based learning, and power point lectures. Difference of opinions is found among students and teachers regarding lecture time duration, accessibility of teachers, small group teaching and use of white board in lectures.

Key words: teachers, students, perspective, teaching methodologies.

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INTRODUCTION:

Quality Medical education is an important factor in the progress of any country. So, suitable approaches, methods, techniques and skills in medical teaching are essential to produce a good number of committed doctors¹. The impact of teaching strategy used by medical colleges play a major role in determining effectiveness of their graduates². Effective teaching depends upon the clarity of objective and content between instructor and the learner. It is observed that what teachers teach and what students learn is different³. Two types of teaching strategies are practiced: teacher-centered & student-centered. In a teacher-centered approach the focus is on the teacher who is viewed as the source of information with no interaction among the students. Student-centered approaches tend to be more collaborative and students work together and interact with the teacher to discover and understand new information⁴. Major hurdle for any teacher is to deliver enormous amount of knowledge in a very tight and narrow schedule⁵. However effective teachers make efficient use of class time, clarify misunderstanding, summarize what has been presented and set high standards for achievement⁶.

A study in India shows that students extremely preferred small group teaching and learning method for discussion (81%), clarification of doubts (86%) and interaction with teacher (92%)¹. Study conducted in Hawler college of medicine in Iraq showed that majority teachers agreed that students are more active in small group teaching and participate in discussions more enthusiastically⁷. Most studies so far within this field have focused on teaching per se while few focus on the teachers⁸. The following study will help to evaluate the satisfaction level of students and teachers regarding the current teaching methodologies.

OBJECTIVES:

The objective of this study is to:

- To evaluate the satisfaction level regarding current teaching system in our college.
- To find out both the preferred and least preferred teaching methods.
- To do a comparative analysis of students' and teachers' perceptions.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:**STUDY DESIGN:**

- Cross sectional study

STUDY SETTING:

- Our research was conducted in Allama Iqbal Medical College.

DURATION OF STUDY:

- Three months

SAMPLE SIZE:

Our sample was 175. Among which 100 were students and 75 were teachers.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE:

- Non probability / purposive sampling

SAMPLE SELECTION:**Inclusion criteria:**

- Medical students of each year and either gender.
- Teachers taking only M.B.B.S classes.

Exclusion criteria:

Students and Teachers were randomly selected.

DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURE:

Data was entered and analyzed in SPSS version 21.0. After entering all the collected data 100 medical students and 75 teachers matching the inclusion criterion were included in our study. Each of them was given a questionnaire comprising of 12 assessment questions intended to evaluate individual preferences for certain teaching methodologies. With every question 5 option likert scale was given with 1 being strongly disagree, 2 disagree, 3 neither agree or disagree, 4 agree, 5 strongly agree. Frequencies and percentages were calculated for each variable. We also did graphical analysis of some variable. Then we applied formulas to calculate mean, standard deviation. Also individual scoring of each respondent was done.

RESULTS AND MAIN FINDINGS:

Among the 175 respondents 100 were students and 75 were teachers. We studied perspective of both teachers and students regarding current teaching methodologies in AIMC and did comparative analysis afterwards. Each respondent was given a 12 question structured questionnaire. Each question referred to a certain teaching methodology being practiced in our medical college. Students and teachers preferences were analyzed on a 5 point Likert scale (in which 1 shows strongly disagree and 5 strongly agree) respectively. All the data collected was analyzed in accordance with the option of strongly agree in the following table which depicts the comparison between their perceptions:

Table 1: Cross tabulation for perception of teachers and students

		Respondents		Total
		Teacher	Students	
Power point lectures are beneficial for delivering lectures.	Count % within respondents	23 34.3%	20 23.3%	43
Animation based lectures have better learning outcomes.	Count % within respondents	26 38.8%	40 46.5%	66
Interactive white board teaching helps to visualize and understand lectures efficiently.	Count % within respondents	16 23.9%	25 29.1%	41
Use of transparency is an effective method of teaching.	Count % within respondents	5 7.5%	12 14.0%	17
Duration of lectures is suitable to attention span of students.	Count % within respondents	18 26.9%	15 17.4%	33
Students are more active during small group teaching.	Count % within respondents	44 65.7%	40 46.5%	84
Practical work enhances understanding of the subject.	Count % within respondents	39 58.2%	39 45.3%	78
Problem based learning in relation to topic of lecture increases understanding of subject.	Count % within respondents	29 43.3%	30 34.9%	59
Interactive student teacher sessions promote conceptual clarity .	Count % within respondents	37 55.2%	31 36.0%	68
Individual capability of teacher in conceptual teaching plays a pivotal role in transferring of knowledge.	Count % within respondents	29 43.3%	46 53.5%	75
Teachers are accessible to students (i-e encourage students to ask them questions and interact with them.)	Count % within respondents	28 41.8%	12 14.0%	40
Current teaching system in AIMC is satisfactory.	Count % within respondents	2 3.0%	5 5.8%	7
Total		67	86	153

Main purpose of our study was to evaluate the satisfaction level among students and teachers about the current teaching system in Allama Iqbal Medical College. The analysis was done to accomplish the above mentioned objective and is graphically represented below:

Graph 1: Current Teaching System

Statistical formulas were applied on our data. Values for mean and standard deviation were calculated. A histogram was plotted for these values and yielded a bell shaped curve which shows the authenticity of our study and is shown below:

Graph 2: Mean and standard deviation

We did further examination and analysis of our data in which we first calculated the score of each respondent and then maximum and minimum scores among all the respondents were found out which are stated in the table below:

Table 2: statistics

score	Valid	175
N	Missing	0
Mean		45.8114
Std. Deviation		5.24940
Minimum		31.00
Maximum		60.00

DISCUSSION:

“Tell me and I forget, teach me and I remember, involve me and I learn” (Benjamin Franklin). Teaching is a two way process in which students and teachers should be equally involved for establishing an effective teaching system. It is therefore essential to find out their perspectives simultaneously. Our study attempted to identify the difference of opinions between the faculty and students regarding the current teaching practices in AIMC.

In our study we found out that majority of teachers and students strongly preferred animation based lectures, practical sessions, problem-based learning. They considered individual capability of teacher in conceptual teaching as an important factor for better learning outcomes. According to both use of transparency is least preferred method. However, response regarding the use of some of the teaching methods was quite variable. As compared to 55.2% of teachers who strongly preferred interactive white board teaching only 36% of students did so. Some ordinary factors like legibility of writing of teachers, variability in vision of students, distance between board and listeners might be the responsible for this difference. Only 17.6% of students are of the view that 45 min lecture duration is suitable to their attention span whereas 26.9% of teachers strongly consider the timing of lectures appropriate. 65.7% of teachers find students more active and attentive in small group sessions however only 46.5% students are comfortable during these sessions. This difference may be on the part of students feeling shy to participate in discussions while it is easy for teachers to get students attention. 14% of students and 41.8% teachers consider teachers accessible to students. This huge difference is because of the mismatch of schedules of teachers and students. Considering the stats regarding satisfaction level of current teaching system in AIMC, among students 33% agree and 5% strongly agree with it whereas among teachers 53.7% agree and 2.7% strongly agree with it. This shows that

there's quite a big room for improvement in the teaching system.

A study conducted in King Edward Medical College showed 50% of the participants approved of the utilization of animation based learning whereas in our setting 46.5% of the students did so⁹. In our college 65.7% and in Hawler College, Iraq 46.9% of faculty members considers small group teachings to be effective. This big difference is due to lack of facilities and infrastructure suitable for proper teaching and already small strength of students due to security purposes as they have mentioned in their article². Regarding the use of white board as an effective teaching methodology, the results of our study are quite similar to the study conducted in Noble medical college, Nepal i.e. 29.1% and 23.6% respectively¹⁰. In our setting and in Rajahmundry Medical College problem based learning was found extremely appropriate teaching method with proportion of 34.9% and 32% respectively¹. 49.6% of students from University of Dundee and 23.3% students from AIMC consider power point lectures beneficial. This is due to the difference in the sample size and country of setting¹¹.

CONCLUSIONS:

- Teachers and students are not fully satisfied with the current teaching methodologies in AIMC.
- There is quite a big room of improvement in the teaching system.
- Difference of opinions is found among students and teachers regarding lecture time duration, accessibility of teachers, small group teaching and use of white board in lectures.
- Whereas both preferred animation based lectures, practical session, problem based learning, and power point lectures.

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QUESTIONNAIRE

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Disagree	Agree	N Agree	Strongly Agree
1. PowerPoint lectures are beneficial for delivering lectures.	1	2	3	4	5	
2. Animation based lectures have better learning outcomes.	1	2	3	4	5	
3. Interactive white board teaching helps visualize & understand lectures efficiently.	1	2	3	4	5	
4. Use of transparency is an effective method of teaching.	1	2	3	4	5	
5. Duration of lectures is suitable to attention span of students.	1	2	3	4	5	
6. Students are more active during small group teaching.	1	2	3	4	5	
7. Practical work enhances understanding of subject.	1	2	3	4	5	
8. Problem based learning in relation to topic lecture increases understanding of subject.	1	2	3	4	5	
9. Interactive student-teacher sessions promote conceptual clarity.	1	2	3	4	5	
10. Individual capability of the teacher conceptual teaching plays a pivotal role in transferring essence of knowledge.	1	2	3	4	5	
11. Teachers are accessible to students (i.e. encourage students to ask them questions and interact with them).	1	2	3	4	5	
12. Current teaching system in AIMC is satisfactory.	1	2	3	4	5	